

Effect of Human Resource Development on Organization Productivity: A Study of Selected Manufacturing Firms in Anambra State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effect of human resource development on organization productivity: A study of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra State. The model's estimates were estimated via multiple econometric model of the ordinary least square to ascertain the effect of Learning and Education (L&E), Experience and Expertise (E&E) and Innovation and Creativity (I&C) on organization productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra State. The results show that Learning and Education (L&E), Experience and Expertise (E&E) and Innovation and Creativity (I&C) have significant impact on productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra State. This study therefore recommends that: Manufacturing firms should strive to employ competent employees in order to improve their productivity. Employees that have developed expertise from experience should be retained and encouraged by firms because they are source of improving productivity. Manufacturing firms should invest in human resource development to produce innovative and Creative (I&C) employees for the organizations. Manufacturing firms should encourage and include Learning and Education (L&E), Experience and Expertise (E&E) and Innovation and Creativity (I&C) in their budget because they have been found to significantly impact on productivity of manufacturing firms.

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KEYWORDS: Human Resource Development, Organization Productivity, Manufacturing Firms

1. INTRODUCTION

Human resource is one of the assets owned by organizations (Wood and Sangstar, 2012). According to Okoye and Ezejiofor (2013) every organization needs three main resources to survive. They are Financial, Material and Human resources. Out of the three resources, researchers have claimed that the human side of an organization is the most important of the three essential resources that an organization needs to be productive (Okoye and Ezejiofor, 2013). Since the human resource of an organization organizes the other two resources that an organization needs to survive, it is therefore plausible and logically discernible to assert that the human side of an organization is the most important of the three essential resources that organizations need to be productive. According to Okoye and Ezejiofor (2013), Human Resource Management (HRM) is the function within an organization that focuses on recruitment of, management of, and providing direction for the people who work in the organization. It is also a strategic

and comprehensive approach of managing people and the work place culture and environment. They further asserted that effective Human resource management enables employees to contribute effectively and productively to the accomplishment of the organization's goals and objectives.

The above role of the human side of an organization notwithstanding, the performance of firms in Nigeria, particularly manufacturing firms have been reported to be low in terms of its survival rate, employment generation and contribution to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (Adenikinju, 2005; Obembe, Adebisi and Adesina, 2011; Sangosanya, 2011). The poor performance of the manufacturing sector is also attributed to the negligence of both public and private organizations in Nigeria as a result their wrong utilization of available human resources (Bukar, Shehu and Idris, 2012). According to Bukar, et al. (2012), the management of some organization does not seem to know the importance of

training and development on workers' productivity. It is erroneously believed by some organizations that if workers have acquired education, there is no need to train them again. Thus, developing the human side of the organization is rarely given the needed attention by organizations. Despite many policies being put in place to ensure workers productivity and efficiency and to possibly stamp out unethical practices in the firms, Human Resource Development is hardly given attention. Consequently, job satisfaction and workers productivity could only be achieved in few establishments.

Presently, the study of human resource management practices as a determinant of organizational performance has gained currency in the last two decades in virtually all sectors - manufacturing and service sector- of most economies (Ayanda, Lawal and Ben-Bernard, 2014; Qureshi, Syed and Mohammad, 2007; Okoye and Ezejiogor, 2013). In this age of competition, one of the most important components for global market entry and development, is to have efficient employees in manufacturing and service sector, So many organizations avoid culture of command and monitoring and go toward synergistic capabilities (Asgarsani, Duostdar and Rostami, 2013). According to Asgarsani, et al. (2013), proper organization and job design are ways that increase employee responsibility in individual, group and team. Therefore, for an organization to be productive there is need for proper use of individuals, providing individual and group progress in a way that makes it possible to develop individuals by educational and training methods that increase the competence and confidence in staff.

Statement of the Problem

This study was necessitated by the declining performance of the Nigeria manufacturing sector. According to Obembe, Adebisi and Adesina (2011), the dismal performance of Nigeria's manufacturing sector is manifested in the high level of graduate unemployment, poverty, corruption and other types of social vices which constitute a threat to the nascent democracy and further investments in Nigeria, thereby perpetuating underdevelopment. Accordingly, Sangosanya (2011) posited that the growth, performance and productivity of Nigeria's manufacturing firms have deteriorated at present and even beyond the rate at which they grew in the past three decades when manufacturing still played significant roles in the Nigerian economy. The Manufacturers Association of Nigeria (MAN) (2009) declared that 820 manufacturing companies have closed down in the past nine years (between 2000 and 2008) of civilian rule and rendered thousands of people jobless, even as the Federal Government said the solution may not be very quick in coming. As observed by Okoli, Edoko and Olise (2014), previous research have found a strong link between human resource development, business experience, education and business Success (Chiliya and Roberts-Lombard, 2012; Wanigasekara and Surangi, 2011; Thapa, 2007). The observed teething problem in this is the persistent decline in the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria despite the strong link between human resource development, business experience, education and business Success in the literature. In resolving this intellectual curiosity, this study therefore investigates the effect of human resource development on organization productivity.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to investigate the effect of human resource development on organization productivity: A study of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Determine the effect of Learning and Education (L&E) on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state.
2. Ascertain the effect of Experience and Expertise (E&E) on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state.
3. Ascertain the effect of Innovation and Creativity (I&C) on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state.

Statement of Hypotheses

- Ho₁:** Learning and Education (L&E) have no significant effect on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state.
- Ho₂:** Experience and Expertise (E&E) have no significant effect on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state.
- Ho₃:** Innovation and Creativity (I&C) have no significant effect on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state.

2. RELATED EMPIRICAL LITERATURE

Ayanda et al, (2014) examined the effects of human resource management practices on financial performance of banks using stepwise regression analysis, Pearson correlation and descriptive statistics to support theoretical models that link HRM practices with financial performance of banks. They found that all tested variables have a positive relation and impact on financial performance of banks but the major contributory practices are selection, training, compensation and employee participation. Abdel-Aziz and Abdel-Naser (2013) examined the Relationship between Human Capital Development and University's Business Performance using descriptive statistics, t-test, ANOVA test, correlation, multiple regressions and stepwise regressions. The result of the study indicated a positive significant relationship between human capital and Middle East University's business performance. Izedonme, Odeyile and Kuegbe (2013) investigated the linkage between human resource accounting and organizational performance in Nigeria using cross-sectional data drawn from the Nigerian Stock Exchange fact book 2009. The regression result revealed that human capital and intangible asset had a positive and insignificant impact on organizational performance. Agwu and Ogiriki (2014) examined human resource development (HRD) and organizational performance in the Nigeria liquefied natural gas company limited, Bonny using descriptive and inferential statistics. They found that significant relationship exists between HRD practices (training and development) and increased employees motivation/commitment and organizational productivity in the Nigeria liquefied natural gas company limited, bonny. Igbaekemen (2014) examined Capacity Building- A Tool for Increase Productivity in Nigeria Public Sector Organization using chi-square statistics. They found there is relationship between capacity building development and organizational productivity. Oforegbunam and Okorafor (2010) examined the effects of human capital development on the performance of small and medium scaled enterprises in the south-eastern region of Nigeria using the multiple regression tool they found that increased human capital development

by sampled SMEs leads to significant improvements in their performances. On-the-job training was identified as the most significant option for developing the human capital of SMEs for enhanced performance. Audu and Gungul (2014) examined the effects of human resource training and development on productivity in Nigerian hospitality industry using mean statistics. They found that training and development improve productivity in the hospitality industry. Young and Choi (2011). The Effects of Human Resource Development on Operational and Financial Performance of Manufacturing Companies using correlation and regression analysis. The study found that financial investment and managerial support for HRD show positive effects on employee commitment but not on competence. Perceived benefits of HRD enhance both employee competence and commitment, whereas the amount of participation in HRD is not a meaningful predictor of those employee outcomes. A series of structural equation models confirms that HRD practices improve employee competence and commitment that have direct effects on operational performance of the organization, which ultimately shapes its financial performance. Anyadike (2013) x-rayed human resource planning and employee productivity in Nigeria public organization. The study observed that human resource planning enhances employee productivity in Nigeria public organization. Gberebie (2012) examined the impact of human resource development and organizational commitment on financial Sector employees in Nigeria using Correlation Matrix and structural equation modelling. The study found that strong impact of human resource development and organizational commitment on performance of employees. Ogbo, Ezeobi and Ituma (2013) carried out a survey on the effect of intellectual capital on organizational performance in the Nigerian banking sector using chi-square statistics. They found that human capital and structural capital have a positive and significant effect on organizational outcomes in the Nigerian banking sector. Funmilayo (2012). The study investigated the influence of human capital formation programmes of the government on job performance effectiveness in industrial organizations in Osun state using descriptive statistics and regression analysis. The study revealed that the human capital development programmes provided for workers have impacted on their job performance effectiveness. Okoye and Ezejiofor (2013) examined the Effect of Human Resources Development on Organizational Productivity using z-test statistical tool. The study found that human resource development is very vital to any organizations ranging from small to large scare enterprise.

In the final analysis, related studies on the effect of human resource development on organization productivity have been investigated from different standpoint and varying literally perspectives. None of the studies reviewed were carried out in Anambra state. Again, most of the studies were carried out outside the shores of the country. However, as a missing gap in the literature, which this study intends to fill, due emphasis has not been given to this research area particularly in Anambra state. This study therefore examines the effect of human resource development on organization productivity: A study of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state.

3. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study adopts a descriptive survey research design which involves asking questions, collecting and analyzing

data from a supposedly representative members of the population at a single point in time with a view to determine the current situation of that population with respect to one or more variable under investigation (Okeke, Olise & Eze, 2008; Chukwuemeka, 2002; Chukwuemeka & Oji, 1999).

Population of the Study

The population of the study consists of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state. Anambra state has a total of eight hundred and thirty six (836) registered manufacturing and allied businesses with the Anambra State Board of Internal Revenue. The above registered manufacturing firms formed the population of the study.

Sample and Sampling Technique(s)

To determine the sample size, for the purpose of questionnaire distribution; the Taro Yamani (1967) formula was used. The formular is stated thus: $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$

Where: n = sample size
N = population
e = Margin of error (5% or 0.05)
I = Constant

Substituting in the above formula:

$$\begin{aligned} N &= \frac{836}{1+836(0.05)^2} \\ &= \frac{836}{1+836(0.0025)} \\ &= \frac{836}{1+2.09} \\ &= \frac{836}{3.09} \\ &= 270.55 \\ &= 271 \end{aligned}$$

Method of Data Collection

The questionnaire was used in collecting data for this study. The first section of the questionnaire contained general information about the sample unit. It included six background questions. The second section was designed to collect information about objectives of the study. All items related to objectives of the study were derived from literature and initial pilot survey of five manufacturing firms' owners. The responses to scale items measuring the effect of human resource development on organization productivity: A study of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state was measured using a structured questionnaire. Two trained research assistants were used for the administration of the questionnaire. They assisted the respondents to complete the questionnaire through an interactive process; however, out of the 271 questionnaires only 182 were dully completed and returned. The analysis was therefore based on the once returned. Using the responses to the questionnaire, the instrument was subjected to reliability test using the Cronbach's Alpha. The Cronbach's Alpha reliability statistics is 0.969 or 97%, which is considered sufficiently high and above the cut-off point of 0.6 suggested by Hair, Bush, and Ortinua (2006) was obtained.

Method of data Analysis

The simple percentage, mean, standard deviation and regression analysis were used to conduct the various analysis of this study. Descriptive statistics like frequencies and percentages were used to elicit information on the demographic profile of the respondents. The regression

analysis was used to evaluate the effect of human resource development on organization productivity.

The productivity of the manufacturing firms is measured thus:

$$\text{Organizational Productivity} = \frac{\text{Firms' Output Level}}{\text{Firms' Input Level}}$$

Model Specification

The essence of economic modelling is to represent the phenomenon under investigation in such a way as to enable the researcher to attribute numerical values to the concept. Using the knowledge gained from the literature, the study examined the effect of human resource development on organization productivity: A study of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state by adopting growth model and modified it to incorporate Learning and Education (L&E), Experience and Expertise (E&E) and Innovation and Creativity (I&C) as the explanatory variables, while Organizational Productivity proxied by the ratio of manufacturing firm out to manufacturing firm input used as the dependent variable. Thus, our model is specified as:

The structural form of the model is:

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

The mathematical form of the model is:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

The econometric form of the model is:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \mu_i \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

- Where Y = Organizational Productivity
- X₁ = Learning and Education (L&E)
- X₂ = Experience and Expertise (E&E)
- X₃ = Innovation and Creativity (I&C)
- β₀ = Intercept of the model
- β₁ – β₃ = Parameters of the regression coefficients
- μ_i = Stochastic error term

4. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Here, we are interested in examining the demographic characteristics of the respondents in order to have knowledge of their background.

Table1: Distribution of respondents according to gender

Options	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	137	75.3
Female	45	24.7
Total	182	100

Source: Field survey, 2017

As shown in table 1, Majority 75.3% of the respondents are males which actually indicate that employment in most of the manufacturing firms are not gender sensitive. Perhaps that could be as a result of nature of job and the production process of the companies.

Table2. Distribution of respondents according to age

Options	Frequency	Percentage (%)
≤ 20	-	-
21-30	11	6.0
31-40	23	12.6
41-50	135	74.2
51-60	13	7.2
61 and above	-	-
Total	182	100

Source: Field survey, 2017

As shown in Table 2. Majority of the respondents which account for over 80% of the responses are over 40 years of age. Which indicates that most of the employees are matured adults and also an indication that recruitment process in the company has not favoured the school leavers and the young graduates in recent time.

Table3.Distribution of respondents according to marital status

Options	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Single	28	15.4
Married	141	77.5
Divorced	4	2.2
Widow/widower	9	4.9
Total	182	100

Source: Field survey, 2017

From table 3, only about 15.4% of the respondents are single. The rest are having had marriage experience. But only 77.5% of the respondents that are married live with their spouse. The implication here is that employees who still stay with their spouse enjoy the support and companionship of such a union and this influences the psyche and mental composition of employees in the organization. Because the performance of an employee facing a divorce case will not doubt the productivity of the employee and the organization.

Table4: Distribution according to respondents position

Options	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Owner,CEO	20	11
Manager	120	65.9
Supervisor	38	20.8
Operational staff	4	2.2
Total	182	100

Source: Field survey, 2017

Owner/CEOs, Managers, Supervisors or the Operational staff of the selected firms responded to the questionnaires administered. As shown in table 4, 11% of the respondents are Owner/CEOs of the selected firms, 65.9% are managers of the selected firms, 20.8% are supervisors, while 2.2% are operational staff.

Table5: Distribution of respondents according to duration of business experience

Options	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Less than one year	11	6.0
1-5 years	18	9.9
6-10 year	44	24.2
11 years and above	109	59.9
Total	182	100

Source: Field survey, 2017

As shown in table 5, responses on duration of business experience shows that majority about 59.9% of the respondents have above 10years of business experience which is an indication that proper motivation and performance has continued to retain them in business.

Table6: Distribution of respondents according to education qualification

Options	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Primary	31	17.0
Secondary	85	46.7
Tertiary	66	36.3
Total	182	100

Source: Field survey, 2017

Table 6 shows that all the employees in the organization are educated as they all had formal education with majority about 46.7% having secondary education. Only 36.3% had tertiary education which is an indication that most of the work carried the company are most likely unskilled jobs that requires training in order to improve the workers performance.

Table7: Descriptive statistics of the effect of Learning and Education (L&E) on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state

Variables	Mean	STD. Dev	Skewness	Kurtosis
Employee's competence	3.682	0.9124	-0.2327	-0.2333
Team work	3.424	0.5432	-0.3114	-1.124
Continuous training	3.552	0.5346	-0.8832	-0.2631
Continuous learning	3.571	0.5424	-0.3114	-1.123
Education average	3.063	0.7915	-0.2753	-0.9612
Knowledge & skills development	3.121	0.7961	-0.2146	-1.364
Market share improvement	3.084	0.7271	-1.283	-1.183

Source: Field survey, 2017

Table 7 shows the descriptive statistics on the effect of Learning and Education (L&E) on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state. From the mean values in Table 1, it can be seen that all the variables (1 – 7) witnessed encouraging degree of influence of effect of Learning and Education (L&E) on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms, with the Employee's competence (1) having the highest mean value.

Table8: Descriptive statistics of the effect of Experience and Expertise (E&E) on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state

Variables	Mean	Standard deviation	Skewness	Kurtosi
Employees are expert	3.992	0.9921	-0.02221	-2.034
Perform at best	3.984	0.9234	-0.5331	-0.5024
Make it different	3.832	0.9112	-0.0522	-1.963
Turn over	3.861	0.8926	-0.4014	-0.2723
Knowledge & skills development	3.823	0.9234	-0.3153	-0.3535
Staff professionalism	3.802	0.9515	-0.3914	-0.1642
Lowest cost/transaction	3.851	0.8912	-0.2626	-0.4813

Source: Field survey, 2017

This table shows the full result of the effect of Experience and Expertise (E&E) on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state. From table 4.8. Items 1 – 7 shows the descriptive statistics related to performance measure. The mean values of the effect of Experience and Expertise (E&E) on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms. From table 4.8, the most influential factor is employees are expert with mean value of 3.992. Followed by perform at best with mean of 3.984.

Table9: Descriptive statistics on the effect of Innovation and Creativity (I&C) on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state

Variables	Mean	Standard deviation	Skewness	Kurtosi
Employees are creative	3.823	0.9234	-0.3153	-0.3535
Voice their opinion	3.802	0.9515	-0.3914	-0.1642
New ideas	3.851	0.8912	-0.2626	-0.4813
New programs launched	3.864	0.8816	-0.4012	-1.036
Knowledge sharing	3.834	0.8814	-0.3031	-0.2945
Satisfaction with innovation.	3.823	0.9234	-0.3153	-0.3535
Motivation & commitment	3.802	0.9515	-0.3914	-0.1642

Source: Field survey, 2017

Table 9 shows the descriptive statistics of the effect of Innovation and Creation (I&C) on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state. Respondents agree that all the items of Innovation and Creation (I&C) impact on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state.

Regression results

Table10. Effect of Human Resource Development on Organization Productivity

	Coefficients	Std. error	t- statistics	Lev.of sig.
(Constants)	1.061	0.286	3.770	.000
Learning and Education (L&E)	1.015	0.054	18.750	.000
Experience and Expertise (E&E)	.597	0.155	3.740	.005
Innovation and Creativity (I&C)	.479	0.113	4.255	.010
R	0.947			
R²	0.897			
Adj. R²	0.882			
F-statistic	59.372			0.000

Source: Computation from field survey, 2017

Dependent variable: The firms' productivity - proxied by the ratio of output to input

In order to evaluate the effect of Learning and Education (L&E), Experience and Expertise (E&E) and Innovation and Creativity (I&C) on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state, the result of the proposed regression model as specified in the methodology was called. Table 10 showed the precision of the model. In general the joint effect of the explanatory variable in the model account for 89.7% of the variations in the effect of Learning and Education (L&E), Experience and Expertise (E&E) and Innovation and Creativity (I&C) on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state.

All the three coefficients [Learning and Education (L&E), Experience and Expertise (E&E) and Innovation and Creativity (I&C)] are significant at 5% level. The implication here is that as the manufacturing firms invest on human resource development it increases the productivity of selected manufacturing firms.

5. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the analysis of the study, it was revealed that:

1. Employee's competence (1) has the highest mean value on the effect of Learning and Education (L&E) on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state.
2. Employees are expert ranks highest on the effect of Experience and Expertise (E&E) on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms.
3. Employees are creativity ranks highest on all the items of Innovation and Creation (I&C) impact on the productivity of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state.
4. Human resource development has helped in achieving Industry leadership, Future outlook, and Overall response to competition, Success rate in new launches, Employee productivity, Sales growth and Profit growth of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra state.
5. Learning and Education (L&E), Experience and Expertise (E&E) and Innovation and Creativity (I&C)] have significant impact on productivity of selected manufacturing firms.

We conclude that human resource development impact on organization productivity. It is also important to note that human resources are unique because they are the only active factor of production that combines other production inputs to obtain the desired outputs; hence they need to be developed through properly articulated HRD policies and procedures. Thus, HRD is the integrated use of training and development, organizational development and career development to improve individual, group and organizational effectiveness.

This study therefore recommends that:

1. Manufacturing firms should strive to employ competent employees in order to improve their productivity.
2. Employees that have developed expertise from experience should be retained and encouraged by firms because they source of improving productivity.
3. Manufacturing firms should invest in human resource development to produce innovative and Creative (I&C) employees for the organizations.

4. Manufacturing firms should encourage and include Learning and Education (L&E), Experience and Expertise (E&E) and Innovation and Creativity (I&C) in their budget because they have been found to significantly impact on productivity of manufacturing firms.

REFERENCES

- [1] Asgarsani, H., Duostdar, O. Rostami, A. (2013). Empowerment and Its Impact on the Organization productivity. *Singaporean Journal of Business Economics, and Management Studies*, 1(9), 25-32.
- [2] Abdel-Aziz, A. S. & Abdel-Naser, I. N. (2013). The Relationship Between Human Capital Development and University's Business Performance. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(6), 104-119.
- [3] Adenikinju, A. (2005) Analysis of the Cost of Infrastructure Failures in Developing Economy: The Case Study of Electricity Sector in Nigeria. AERC Research Paper 148, African Economic Research Consortium, Nairobi.
- [4] Agwu, M.O & Ogiriki, T. (2014). Human Resource Development and Organizational Performance in the Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas Company Limited, Bonny. *Journal of Management and Sustainability*, 4(4), 134-146.
- [5] Anyadike, N. O. (2013) Human Resource Planning and Employee Productivity in Nigeria Public Organization. *Global Journal of Human Resource Management*, 1(4), 56-68.
- [6] Asgarsani, H., Duostdar, O. & Rostami, A. (2013). Empowerment and its Impact on the Organization Productivity. *Singaporean Journal of Business Economics, and Management Studies*, 1(9), 25-32.
- [7] Audu, J. S. & Gungul, T. (2014). Effects of Human Resource Training and Development on Productivity in Nigerian Hospitality Industry. *International Journal of Public Administration and Management Research (IJPAMR)*, 2(2):80-87.
- [8] Ayanda, A. M., Lawal, O. R. & Ben-Bernard, P. (2014). Effects of Human Resource Management Practices on Financial Performance of Banks. *Transnational Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(2), 1-16.
- [9] Bukar, S., Shehu, A. B. & Idris, A. (2012). The Effect of Human Resource Management on Productivity of Workers in Nigeria. *Journal of Business and Organizational Development*, 4(1), 54-59.
- [10] Chiliya, N., & Roberts-Lombard, M. (2012). Impact of levels of education and experience on profitability of small grocery shops in South Africa. *International Business Management*, 3(1), 462-470.
- [11] Chukwuemaka, E. E. O. (2002). *Research Method and Thesis Writing: A Multi-Disciplinary Approach*. Enugu, HRV Publishers.
- [12] Chukwuemaka, E. E. O. and Oji, O. R. (1999). *Applied Social and Behavioural Research: Guidelines for Thesis Writing*. Enugu, John Jacob's Classic Publishers.
- [13] Funmilayo, S. B. (2012). Influence of human capital formation programme on job Performance effectiveness in selected industrial organizations in

- Osun state, Nigeria. *Journal of Social Science and Public Policy*, 4(12), 30-41.
- [14] Gberevbie, D. E.(2012). Impact of Human Resource Development and Organizational Commitment on Financial Sector Employees in Nigeria. *Scientific Annals of the "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iasi Economic Sciences*, 59 (2), 29-41.
- [15] Hair, J.F; Bush, R.P. and Ortinau, D.J. (2006). *Marketing Research. McGraw Hill/Irwin*, New York.
- [16] Igbaekemen, G. O. (2014). Capacity Building- A Tool for Increase Productivity in Nigeria Public Sector Organization. *Global Journal of Human Resource Management*, 2(3), 45-58.
- [17] Izedonme, P. F., Odeyile, L. G. & Kuegbe, K. (2013). Human Resource Accounting and its Impact on Organisational Performance. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*,4(15), 50-55.
- [18] Obembe, O. B., Adebisi, S. A. & Adesina, J. A. (2011). Bank Loans, Ownership structure and Efficiency of Listed Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria. *Advances in Manufacturing and Applied Economics*, 1 (2), 221-236.
- [19] Oforegbunam, T. E. & Okorafor, G. F. (2010). Effects of Human Capital Development on the Performance of Small and Medium Scaled Enterprises in the South-eastern Region of Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 12(8), 49-58.
- [20] Ogbo, A., Ezeobi, J. & Ituma, A. (2013). Impact of Intellectual Capital on Organisational Performance: Evidence from Nigeria Banking Sector. *JORIND*, 11(2), 249-254.
- [21] Okeke, T.C., Olisa, M.C. and Eze, G.A. (2008), *Research Methods in Business and Management Sciences*. Enugu- Nigeria. lyke Ventures Production.
- [22] Okoye, P.V.C. & Ezejiolor, R. A.(2013). The Effect of Human Resources Development on Organizational Productivity. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 3(10), 250-268.
- [23] Qureshi, M., Tahir Hijazi, T., Syed, R., & Mohammad, I. (2007). Impact of Human Resource Management Practices on Pakistani organizations. *Journal of Business Policy Resource*, 3(2), 128- 138.
- [24] Sagosanya, A. O. (2011). Firms Growth Dynamics in Nigeria's Manufacturing Industry: A panel Analysis. *Journal of Applied Econometric Review*, 1(1): 2-15
- [25] Young, S. S. & Choi, J. N. (2011). *The Effects of Human Resource Development on Operational and Financial Performance of Manufacturing Companies: A Large-Scale, Longitudinal Analysis*. Institute for Research on Labour and Employment, <http://escholarship.org/uc/item/5xz8p7bk>
- [26] Wanigasekara .W.M.S.K and Surangi H.K.N.S (2011). Impact of level of education and business experience on business success among small retail owner managers in Sri Lanka, University of kelaniya. Paper to be presented at 2nd International Conference on Business and Information (ICBI) 20 October 2011. [Online]. Available: <http://www.kln.ac.lk/fcms/ICBI2011/images/ICBM/dccs/Microsoft%20Word%20-%20ENP001.pdf> [Accessed: 18 Aug. 2011].
- [27] Wood, F & Sangster, A. (2012). *Business Accounting* (12th Ed.). Prentice Hall for Management (3rd.Ed). John Willey & Sons, Inc: USA.